

Survey link: <https://forms.gle/osEsjVqVk9yh6Mwk8>

Sección 1 de 3

Pattern-based requirements engineering for creating MedTech software

Thank you for being so interested in our project!

We have prepared a survey to show a use case of our project and collect relevant data for further design improvement.

We will present you with a use case from a company that requires developing a MedTech application. After answering the demographic questionnaire and reading the comic strip, completing this survey will take **5 min** approx.

Correo *

Correo válido

Este formulario registra los correos. [Cambiar configuración](#)

First things first: **Ethical agreement**

With this survey, we plan to collect data from potential users of our project results. We will ask for a short demographic questionnaire and about your experience on developing software based on requirements patterns. You are free to withdraw at any time to answer the survey. All data will be made anonymous and will be treated as confidential. There are no benefits to you as a participant, and there are no foreseeable risks to you for participating or declining to answer the survey.

We will use the collected data for scientific and academic proposes only, and the data may store in anonymised form in a data repository.

If you have any questions or concerns about the collected data, don't hesitate to get in touch with one of the following people:

Dr Marcela Ruiz, Senior Lecturer and Research in Software Engineering at the ZHAW-IniT, ruiz@zhaw.ch

David Mosquera, PhD (c) and Research Assistant at the ZHAW-IniT, mosq@zhaw.ch

Do you agree to let us collect our data? *

- Yes, I agree to let collect my data.
- No, I do not agree to let collect my data.

Thank you! Now, let us know more about you: **Demographic Questionnaire**

Descripción (opcional)

What is your educational background? (e.g., Software engineering, Health sciences, Medicine, ^{*} Pharmaceuticals, Software development, etc.)

Texto de respuesta larga

How much experience in requirements engineering do you have? (including participating as a ^{*} client or product owner)

- No experience
- Less than 1 year
- More than 1 year but less than 2 years
- More than 2 years but less than 5 years
- More than 5 years

Had you ever participated in developing a MedTech software application? ^{*}

- Yes
- No

In which country do you work?

Texto de respuesta corta

What is your current role in your organization? (e.g. Requirements engineer, Software engineer, Developer, Medicine doctor, Innovation manager, etc.)

Texto de respuesta larga

Which is the size (number of employees) of the organization you work with? (approx)

Texto de respuesta corta

Which is the sector of the organization you work with? (e.g., Telecommunication, embedded ^{*} systems, Healthcare, etc.)

Texto de respuesta corta

Similarly like Randy, when in your team you find a requirement similar to a previously developed requirement, do you apply any requirement reuse techniques?

- Yes
- No

If yes, which requirement reuse technique do you use?

Texto de respuesta larga

If not, what do you usually do when you find a requirement similar to a previous developed requirement?

Texto de respuesta corta

Would you adopt LEMON for reusing software requirements?

- Yes
- No
- Maybe

What could be the barriers for successful adoption of LEMON in your team?

Texto de respuesta larga

What do you think is missing in LEMON to be useful in practice?

Texto de respuesta larga

Which would be the perfect interaction (i.e., how you provide the data to LEMON) for reusing requirement patterns in your projects?

Texto de respuesta larga

Do you have any other comment or question about LEMON? Let us know in the text below!

Texto de respuesta larga
